

Numerical investigation of the electric field produced in normal and cancer cells by the interaction with helium plasma jet

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In recent years, the atmospheric pressure plasma jet has gained a lot of attention due to its low production costs and therapeutic effects. These effects are mainly attributed to the production of radicals which collide with the living tissue and the high electric field generated in the intracellular region [1]. Furthermore, it has been widely reported that plasma energy interacts differently with healthy and cancerous tissue[2,3]. To elucidate this phenomenon the direct contact of helium plasma jet with living tissues (healthy skin and skin affected by cancer) and the resulting intracellular electric field were studied by using numerical modelling. A two-dimensional axisymmetric model was built for the analytical description of the helium plasma jet at atmospheric pressure, taking into account the present of dry air impurities. The configuration of the simulation is similar to the experimental setup of [4]. The equations and boundary conditions used in the model are described in [5]. In the plasma an optimized chemistry was used which consider 13 species and 25 reaction channels. For the description of the healthy skin only the outer layer is taken into account, the epidermis. This layer mainly composed of four layers: the stratum basalis, the stratum spinosum, the stratum granulosum, and the stratum corneum. On the other hand, the skin affected by cancer was modelled to be composed from the stratum corneum and a layer of melanoma. Due to the computational complexity of having to incorporate in the model the analytical intracellular structure of the previous tissues, average values of the electrical properties have been used for the description of the normal skin and the skin affected by cancer. The electrical properties are taken from [5].

The electric field calculated in the region of the normal skin and the skin affected by cancer was subsequently used in a new model which consider the analytical geometry of a normal and a cancer cells. These cells mainly consist of the cell membrane, the cytoplasm, the nucleus membrane and the nucleus. The geometrical and the electrical properties of the cells are taken from [5]. Our calculation shows that a higher electric field is produced in cancer cells than in normal cells. In this work we also explore effect the higher intra membrane electric field has on cell viability and growth.

References

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